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8 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 3

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CHANGES IN THE QUALITY OF LIFE INDICATORS OF PATIENTS WHEN ALLERGIC RHINITIS IS COMORBID WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN

For citation: Mirrakhimova Kh. Maktuba, Saidkhonova M. Adibakhon. Changes in the quality of life indicators of patients when allergic rhinitis is comorbid with bronchial asthma in children // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2023, vol. 8, issue 3, pp.162-168

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8165988>

ANNOTATION

In this article, the results of the study of indicators of quality of life of patients with bronchial asthma combined with allergic rhinitis in children are highlighted. The study was conducted in the children's allergology department of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy. The indicators of quality of life in children under examination are "nasal symptoms", "general symptoms", the severity of practical problems in patients with various nosological forms of allergic rhinitis, indicators of negative symptoms, limitation of activity due to general AR - 65%, with BA - 68% and AR +BA comorbid when - 88.0% of patients had unsatisfactory results.

Keywords: allergic rhinitis, bronchial asthma, children, quality of life, comorbid.

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ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ БОЛЬНЫХ ПРИ КОМОРБИДНОМ АЛЛЕРГИЧЕСКОМ РИНИТЕ С БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМОЙ У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье освещены результаты изучения показателей качества жизни больных бронхиальной астмой в сочетании с аллергическим ринитом у детей. Исследование проводилось в отделении детской аллергологии многопрофильной клиники Ташкентской медицинской академии. Показатели качества жизни обследуемых детей: «назальные симптомы», «общие симптомы», выраженность практических проблем у больных с различными нозологическими формами аллергического ринита, показатели негативной симптоматики, ограничение активности вследствие общего АР - 65 %, при БА - 68% и при коморбидной АР+БА - 88,0% больных имели неудовлетворительные результаты.

Ключевые слова: аллергический ринит, бронхиальная астма, дети, качество жизни, коморбид.

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БОЛАЛАРДА АЛЛЕРГИК РИНИТНИ БРОНХИАЛ АСТМА БИЛАН КОМОРБИД КЕЧИШИДА БЕМОРЛАРДА ҲАЁТ СИФАТИ КЎРСАТГИЧЛАРИДА ЎЗГАРИШЛАР

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада болаларда аллергик ринит, аллергик ринит билан биргаликда кечган бронхиал астмали беморларнинг ҳаёт сифати кўрсаткичларини ўрганишдаги натижалар ёритилган. Тадқиқот Тошкент тиббиёт академияси кўп тармоқли клиникасининг болалар аллергология бўлимида ўтказилган. Текширувдаги болаларда ҳаёт сифати кўрсаткичлари “бурун белгилари”, “умумий белгилар”, аллергик ринитнинг турли нозологик шакллари бўлган беморларда амалий муаммоларнинг оғирлиги, салбий аломатлар кўрсаткичлари, фаолиятнинг чекланиши туфайли умумий АР билан - 65%, БА билан - 68% ва АР +БА коморбид келганда - 88,0% беморларда қониқарсиз натижалар қайд этилган.

Калит сўзлар: аллергик ринит, бронхиал астма, болалар, ҳаёт сифати, коморбид.

In the world, the rate of comorbidity of allergic rhinitis with bronchial asthma is increasing day by day, especially in economically developing countries. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), "... allergic rhinitis comorbidity with bronchial asthma occurs in 18% to 45% of children and more" [2,8,9]. It is known that "... the prevalence of the disease in different countries is on average up to 4 cases per 1000 children". In many countries of the world, the constant increase in the number of children with allergic rhinitis is due to patients' misinterpretation of the symptoms of the disease, failure to consult a pediatric allergist in time, failure to perform diagnosis and treatment on time, which shows the severity of the problem. [1,4,6,7] In children with various forms of allergic disease, quality of life indicators are changed, which are important not only for patients, but also for the whole family [3,10,12,13].

Among the topical issues of modern allergology, the problem of allergic rhinitis (AR) in children has a special place [1,5,9,11]. Allergic rhinitis is one of the common allergic diseases in childhood [2,3,12]. This disease is a global problem, because it has a high specific place in allergic pathology (60-70%) and is also common in the pediatric population (10-15%), which emphasizes the importance of this problem [4,6,10,12].

In many countries of the world, the constant increase in the number of children with allergic rhinitis is due to patients' misinterpretation of the symptoms of the disease, failure to consult a pediatric allergist in time, failure to perform diagnosis and treatment on time, which shows the severity of the problem.

The purpose of the study: to study indicators of the quality of life of bronchial asthma patients with allergic rhinitis in children.

Materials and research methods. The study was conducted in the pediatric allergology department of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Toshken Medical Academy. Allergic rhinitis, bronchial asthma, and bronchial asthma combined with allergic rhinitis were examined. The age of patients diagnosed with allergic rhinitis was from 7 to 12 years, and the average age was 9.1 ± 0.31 .

All patients underwent a questionnaire designed and adapted by the ARIA program aimed at identifying or confirming "Allergic Rhinitis" before coming to the clinic. When all patients were asked for anamnesis information, it was found that they had not only AR clinical symptoms, but also BA clinical symptoms (asphyxia attacks, acute cough, wheezing). Standard clinical, allergological and immunological diagnostic methods were used to diagnose allergic rhinitis and bronchial asthma.

When studying nasal symptoms from the point of view of quality of life, they were examined in the entire group of patients with different nosological forms of AR. "Nasal congestion" was the least expressed in AR patients (3.20 ± 0.16) compared to AR +BA group (4.21 ± 0.28) $r < 0.05$. In AR patients with AR, the "runny nose" became apparent during periodic or significant contact with

allergens. In this category of patients, nasal congestion became permanent during the period of sensitization by allergens due to the progression of the disease. AR+BA patients had higher values of "runny nose" (4.21±0.28), children in this group had both allergic and inflammatory runny nose, which was less severe than AR patients.

"Rhinorrhea" was more observed in comorbid disease compared to AR (2.47±0.23) and AR+BA (4.24±0.18) and it had a continuous character $r < 0.001$. "Sneezing" occurred at the same frequency in all patients, significantly, no difference was found between groups, $r > 0.05$. "Nasal itching" was significantly expressed in patients with AR+BA (4.61±0.19) compared to patients with AR (3.85±0.21) ($r < 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 1

Evaluation of indicators of "nasal signs" in children under investigation

Groups Simtoms	AR n=40	AR+BA n=33
	M±m	M±m
Runny nose	3,20±0,16	4,21±0,28*
Rhinorrhea	2,47±0,23	4,64±0,23**
Sneezing	2,45±0,22	3,24±0,18*
Itchy nose	3,85±0,21	4,61±0,19*

Note: ** $r < 0.001$ - significance of differences between groups 1 and 2;

The "common symptoms" of AR were also studied, such as daytime fatigue, weakness, decreased learning, decreased concentration, thirst, and headaches. When comparing these indicators between groups, it was found that all these indicators were significantly expressed in patients with AR+BA $r < 0.001$.

In the AR group, patients with AR+BA had a lower rate of attention deficit compared to patients with BA. In patients with AR, no "general symptoms" were observed in the absence of the main symptoms of AR during the remission period of the disease, but during the exacerbation of the disease, these symptoms episodically affected the child's daily life, resulting in a decrease in the quality of life index. AR+BA patients in group 3 had a serious impact on quality of life indicators due to inflammation and allergic process during the exacerbation of the disease. As a result of the progression of the disease in patients with BA, many patients adapted to their condition and this indicator almost did not bother them, $r > 0.05$ (Table 2).

The relationship between quality of life indicators "general symptoms" and the main symptoms of AR was studied.

Table 2

Assessment of indicators of quality of life according to "common symptoms" in children with different nosological forms of allergic disease

Groups Signs	AR n=40	AR+BA n=39	BA n=33
	M±m	M±m	M±m
Daytime fatigue	2,75±0,23	4,23±0,14***	2,74±0,24
Dry mouth "thirst"	3,12±0,24*	4,39±0,11***	3,10±0,27**
A decrease in the assimilation of the lesson	2,55±0,23*	4,83±0,34 ***	3,69±0,13**
Fatigue	2,63±0,26*	5,52±0,24 ***	3,77±0,24**
Decreased concentration	2,3±0,21	3,9±0,12	2,71±0,35
Headache	2,13±0,24*	4,84±0,12***	3,34±0,29**

Note: * $r < 0.001$ - significance of differences between groups 1 and 2.

Patients with AR showed a moderate, direct correlation ($r = 0.48-0.43$) between nasal and general symptoms ($r < 0.05$). The main symptoms of children in this category are not related to general symptoms, because the duration of the disease was at least 1 month, and the symptoms were quickly eliminated, and did not affect the quality of life of the child.

With BA, it was found that stuffy nose, sneezing, and reduced learning ($r = 0.57$) and the symptom "stuffy nose" affected the feeling of dry mouth (thirst) ($r = 0.506$), $r < 0.01$.

AR+BA patients experienced fatigue ($r = 0.72$), headache ($r = 0.69$), weakness ($r = 0.58$), decreased learning ($r = 0.55$) due to prolonged nosebleeds. < 0.01 . Correlation was found between the sensation of nasal itching and dry mouth ($r = 0.75$), ($r < 0.01$).

In patients with uncontrolled symptoms of AR, failure to adhere to a hypoallergenic regimen and diet during exacerbations, as well as neglecting symptomatic treatment, have resulted in practical problems. Practical problems - these are the problems that the patient has to experience in daily life during the exacerbation of AR, which worsens the quality of life of the patient and his family. In children with AR, due to a large amount of rhinorrhea, there was a need to always carry a handkerchief, which caused problems for the child and his family (3.9 ± 0.1) ($r < 0.001$).

The practical problem "forced nose rubbing" was caused by itching in the nasal cavity during the exacerbation of the disease in children and was found more than in patients with BA $r < 0.001$. Patients in the AR+BA group had significantly less practical problems compared to BA patients with AR ($r < 0.01$) (Table 3).

Table 3

Severity of practical problems in patients with different nosological forms of allergic rhinitis

Groups	AR	BA	AR+BA
	n=40	n=30	n=33
Practical problems	M±m	M±m	M±m
The need to carry a handkerchief	3,33±0,18***	1,51±0,16****	2,55±0,26*****
Compulsive nose rubbing	3,78±0,18*	4,23±0,12****	3,33±0,23***
Compulsion to snore	3,5±0,17***	1,38±0,15****	2,45±0,24*****

Note: * $r < 0.001$ - significance of differences between groups 1 and 2. ** $r < 0.05$ - significance of differences between groups 1 and 3. *** $r < 0.01$ - significance of differences between groups 2 and 3.

A correlation was found between rhinorrhea and the need to carry handkerchiefs in AR patients ($r = 0.57$), $p < 0.01$. Nasal congestion affected all practical problems, as indicated by a significant correlation between nasal symptoms and the severity of practical problems ($r = 0.7; 0.69; 0.51$), $r < 0.01$. A significant correlation was observed between itching of the nose and the practical actions performed by the patient ($r = 0.81; 0.42; 0.8$) $r < 0.01$. A positive, direct correlation was observed in BA patients with AR induction of nasal itching and the need to rub the nose frequently during the day ($r = 0.82$), as well as practical problems in the form of stuffy nose and the need to blow the nose ($r = 0.65$) $p < 0.01$.

Severe nasal itching in AR+BA patients in group 3 affected the severity of all practical problems, resulting in an inverse, strong correlation ($r = 0.8; 0.94; 0.61$), $r < 0.01$. A severe runny nose during an exacerbation requires significant practical problems with the need to carry a handkerchief and rub the nose ($r = 0.82; 0.59$). Practical problems were clearly observed in this group, as the presence of a joint factor of inflammation and allergic genesis in the process was confirmed ($r < 0.01$).

Patients with different nosological forms of the disease have negative emotional symptoms associated with the course of the main disease, which is also important for the quality of life of the patient and his family (Table 4).

Table 4

Indicators of negative symptoms in children with different nosological forms of the disease

Groups Side effect (Negative) characters	AR n=40	BA n=39	AR+BA n=33
	M±m	M±m	M±m
Resentment	2,72±0,21*	3,18±0,16* ^{****}	4,33±0,26 ^{***}
Anger, impatience	2,81±0,22*	2,08±0,10* ^{****}	3,93±0,25 ^{***}
Getting nervous	3,4±0,14*	3,26±0,09* ^{****}	4,56±0,28 ^{***}
Congestion, embarrassment	2,8±0,28	3,2±0,18	4,85±0,23 ^{***}

Note: *r < 0.05 - significance of differences between groups 1 and 2. **r < 0.05 - significance of differences between groups 1 and 3. ***r < 0.01 - significance of differences between groups 2 and 3.

Patients with AR+BA often showed negative symptoms such as irritability (4.56±0.28), anger (3.93±0.25) and resentment (4.33±0.26) during the exacerbation of the disease. <0.01. No significant differences were found in the analysis of negative symptoms during disease progression when comparing the AR and BA groups. Compression was detected in patients of all groups, but its frequency did not have significant differences (r>0.05) when comparing between the examined groups.

In the group with AR, emotional lability was noted, during the period of AR exacerbation, it was manifested by embarrassment and frustration from a runny nose during the day, an inverse, moderate correlation was noted (r=0.52, 0.41), (p <0.01). Frequent sneezing caused a feeling of discomfort (r=0.5), (p <0.01). Moderate and direct correlation r<0.05 was found as sneezing caused feelings of nervousness (r=0.39) and embarrassment (r=0.49) together with emotional lability.

A moderate, direct correlation was found between emotional lability in the form of nasal symptoms (sneezing) and feeling of discomfort during the exacerbation of the disease with BA (r=0.49), r<0.01. Mild or absent runny nose, sneezing, and coughing did not affect emotional symptoms in children in this group, as no correlation was found between them. With the persistence of the disease, patients have already adapted to these conditions, and they did not affect the emotional state of the child and did not worsen the quality of life.

In the 3rd group with AR+BA, due to severe itching, the child had a feeling of irritability and anger, irritability (r = 0.8; 0.6), (r < 0.01). A significant, direct correlation was noted between nosebleeds and emotional symptoms, i.e. child's resentment, anger and embarrassment (r =0.65, r=0.51; 0.59) r<0.01. Nosebleeds during exacerbation of AR significantly affected the child's emotional state, worsened the quality of life of the patient and his family.

The concept of general activity limitation in children with AR+BA includes assessment of impairment in daytime functioning, learning ability, peer communication problems, and reluctance to play sports. Activity limitation in these children is a decrease in daily activity (5.27±0.20), learning difficulties (4.58±0.4), difficulties in communicating with peers (4.91±0.1) and reluctance to play sports. (4.42±0.3) was observed r<0.001. In patients with AR and BA, the indicators of general activity limitation had almost the same values (Table 5).

Table 5

Indicators of general activity limitation in children with various forms of allergic rhinitis

Groups	AR n=40	BA n=39	AR+BA n=33
Limited activity	M±m	M±m	M±m
	Daytime activity disorder	2,78±0,17*	2,8±0,22* ^{****}
Absorption slows down	2,9±0,24*	3,6±1,15* ^{****}	4,58±0,4 ^{***}
Disruption of communication with peers	1,45±0,27*	1,2±0,14* ^{****}	4,91±0,1 ^{***}
Reluctance to do sports	2,03±0,23*	2,1±0,2* ^{****}	4,42±0,3 ^{***}

Sleep disturbance

2,38±1,95***

2,28±0,75*****

3,79±1,5*****

Note: * $r < 0.001$ - significance of differences between groups 1 and 2. ** $r < 0.05$ - significance of differences between groups 1 and 3. *** $r < 0.001$ - significance of differences between groups 2 and 3.

In patients with allergic rhinitis, runny nose limited the child's daytime activity in the period of exacerbation of AR ($r=0.52$), and sneezing caused discomfort in sports ($r < 0.01$). All indicators of limitation of activity in patients with BA were expressed, but nasal symptoms did not affect the course of the disease, only a correlation was found between nasal stuffiness and a decrease in daily activity ($r = 0.56$), ($r < 0.01$). In this group of patients, obvious hypoxia is detected, but due to the persistence of the disease, the patients have adapted to their condition.

In group 3 children with AR+BA, there is a correlation between persistent nosebleeds and activity limitations, for example: a correlation was noted between decreased daily activity ($r=0.61$) and educational process ($r=0.5$). Sneezing caused limitations in sports activities ($r=0.6$; 0.51). Strong itching in the nasal cavity was observed to be related to activity restrictions, for example: a correlation between daily activities ($r=0.69$), sports ($r=0.58$) was found, $r < 0.01$.

In patients with different nosological forms of AR, problems with sleep disorders reduced daily activity, limited the desire to play sports, which subsequently led to a decrease in the ability of patients to study, learn ($r = 0.69$) and communicate with peers ($r = 0.57$). A clear and direct correlation was noted between sleep disturbances and behavioral problems in this group of patients with AR. In patients with BA, sleep problems were reflected in the educational process only during the exacerbation of the disease, a moderate, direct correlation ($r=0.48$) was found, $r < 0.01$. In patients with AR+BA in group 3, sleep disturbance affected the educational process ($r=0.7$) and reluctance to do sports ($r=0.67$). In this group of patients, the correlation was significant and direct, because under the influence of two factors, i.e. inflammation and allergic processes together aggravated the course of the main disease. Subjective evaluation of the condition, i.e., the well-being of patients, includes evaluation of the quality of life as good, satisfactory and unsatisfactory.

Thus, 65% of patients with AR, 68% with BA, and 88.0% of patients with combined AR +BA assessed their general condition as unsatisfactory due to limitation of general activity.

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БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 3

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
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